

SCLEROTHERAPY OF ESOPHAGEAL VARICES

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***Annotation.** With the introduction of the endoscopy method into clinical practice, it became possible to use endoscopes to perform sclerotherapy of esophageal varices. Endoscopic surgery is aimed at stopping bleeding and preventing recurrent bleeding. It is considered more justified to use large-diameter surgical fibroendoscopes such as TQF-2D "Olimpus" (Japan) in combination with local anesthesia, which makes esophagoscopy less traumatic. Endoscopic sclerotherapy of esophageal varices can be performed in two ways: by para- or intravascular administration of special drugs (1-3% thrombovar). According to J. Tarblancke et al., the indication for endoscopic sclerotherapy of esophageal varices is: Esophageal variceal bleeding in patients for whom surgical treatment is contraindicated, bleeding from single esophageal varices (Q Salem et al.), patients with a high risk of recurrent bleeding.*

***Key words:** gastrit, gastroduadenid, anemia, gastroenterology,*

Introduction. Due to the introduction of the endoscopic occlusion of esophageal varices into clinical practice, the mortality rate of patients with bleeding has significantly decreased, and a decrease in the frequency of their intensity and duration has been noted. For injection of the drug, NM-1 "Olimpus" type injectors (Japan) are most often used. Paravasal administration of drugs begins directly from the cardiac region of the stomach and continues between varicose veins at intervals of 1-3 cm in the oral direction. An average of 2-5 ml of the drug is spent on each submucosal administration, while the total amount of the substance reaches 40-60 ml. In addition, with large venous nodes of the esophagus, submucosal administration of the drug is performed to the right and left of the node, which achieves better compression of the vein walls with paravasal infiltrate. After this, intravenous administration of the drug is possible. The advantage of submucosal administration of sclerosing agents over intravenous is greater safety, since intense

bleeding from the site of vessel puncture is possible, in addition, intravenous injections into varicose nodes in portal hypertension can disrupt collateral circulation in other organs. Repeated sclerotherapy sessions are technically no different from primary treatment. The main advantage of this treatment method is stopping bleeding, although sometimes temporary, which makes it possible to save the patient's life and develop tactics for further treatment, in addition, this method is used for prophylactic purposes, which helps prevent possible bleeding. We used a 3% solution of thrombovar as a sclerosant. During endoscopic sclerotherapy at the height of bleeding, the intravascular method was used in 3 patients and the paravascular method of sclerosant administration was used in 9 patients. In 46 patients with cirrhosis with stopped bleeding, a combined method of sclerotherapy was used.

Materials and methods of research. Since bleeding from the upper gastrointestinal tract caused by dilation of varicose veins of the esophagus and cardiac part of the stomach directly threatens the life of a patient with liver cirrhosis with portal hypertension, conservative treatment often does not lead to the desired result, therefore, methods of direct surgical intervention on bleeding vessels are used. For direct intervention on veins, M.D. Patsiora (1967) proposed a technique of submucous residence of varicose veins of the cardiac part of the stomach and cardioesophageal junction in a checkerboard pattern by gastrotomy and machine access. The operation modified by M.D. Patsiora is performed in the following order - after laparotomy, the anterior wall of the stomach on the border of the fundus with the body of the stomach is opened in an oblique direction from the bottom to the lesser curvature for 10 cm. The upper part of the anterior wall of the stomach is lifted. The dilated veins of the cardiac part of the stomach are sutured with catgut through the mucous membrane with interrupted sutures. By pulling the ligatures and pressing the mucous membrane, the veins of the cardioesophageal junction and even the lower part of the esophagus bulging into the lumen are sutured in a checkerboard pattern. Then the gastric wound is sutured.

Results and discussion. In search of an alternative intervention with minimal trauma, absolute hemostatic efficiency, long-term prevention of bleeding from varicose veins, our employees (F.G.Nazirov, A.A. Mansurov, 1998) developed an original method of total disconnection of the gastroesophageal collector. The technique of the proposed method of operation is as follows. After upper-midline laparotomy, starting from the border of the middle and upper thirds, the stomach is mobilized along the lesser and greater curvature to the abdominal part of the esophagus with the lowering of the fundus of the stomach from the diaphragm. If technically necessary, splenectomy is permissible, but undesirable. The trunks of the vagus nerve

are raised on holders. Along the cardiac line of the stomach or 1.5-2.0 cm below it along the entire length from the lesser to the greater curvature of the stomach, the anterior and posterior walls of the stomach are sutured through all layers with tantalum staples of the UKL-60 mechanical suturing apparatus (AC RUz IHDP 04431 dated 28.07.2000). Or along the same line around the entire stomach, a ligature is applied (AC RUz IHDP 04430 dated 21.07.2000) like a purse-string suture. This achieves complete separation of the blood circulation of the cardiac section of the stomach and esophagus from the portal system. Continuity of the gastrointestinal tract is restored by anastomosis between the abdominal esophagus and the subcardiac stomach if the level of disconnection corresponds to the cardiac stomach, or by cardio-fundal gastro-gastric anastomosis if the level of disconnection lies below the cardiac line of the stomach. Thus, the mechanical suture or the dissociating ligature remains under the posterior wall of the anastomosis. The operation is completed by fundoplication and nasogastric drainage. The portosystemic shunting technique was not included in any of the analysis groups presented in this study. However, it was the possibility of its implementation in the surgical departments of the RRCEM and its branches as one of the effective means of long-term prevention of recurrent bleeding in patients with cirrhosis with stopped bleeding from the varicose veins and esophagus that was the goal of the scientific study and the top of the pyramid of the created diagnostic and tactical-therapeutic algorithms. By the time this study was completed, the first such operations had already been performed in the Namangan, Andijan and Urgench branches of the RRCEM. Without dwelling on the detailed description of the portosystemic shunting technique, we considered it appropriate to provide in this chapter a diagram and a real view of the most accessible type to perform - distal splenorenal anastomosis according to W. Warren

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